

Paper 3

THE LINGUA FRANCA OF 21ST CENTURY SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

21st century witnesses a tremendous agitation in every field. Education in its fullest sense, fully equipped to shape the future citizens to compete the world of turmoil with their full potential. But the education system unaware of the important threat of making students to cope with the reality. Parents, teachers and even the stakeholders are merely focusing on to the near future whereas the younger ones are to be moulded for a life time. The moment they get graduated and opens up to the world of 'Startups', they witness a huge gap between the reality and the theories they have learned. We educate children for a better job with technologies and lots more but the world they have to encounter with, is really a contrary version of what they have thought of. When the 21st century demands us to be critical and creative; teaching, learning and evaluation itself should transform to suit to fit the needs of today. Obsolete pedagogy and methodology in no way help the students to foster the skills needed for 21st century. Desiderata of Lingua Franca should be made mandatory so as to enhance the capabilities of the 21st century students.

Keywords: 21st century skills, Lingua Franca of 21st century, desiderata of English

INTRODUCTION

21st century witnesses a tremendous agitation in every field. Education in its fullest sense, fully equipped to shape the future citizens to compete the world of turmoil with their full potential. But the education system lacks the important threat of making students to cope with the reality. Parents, teachers and even the stakeholders are merely focusing on to the near future whereas the younger ones are to be moulded for a life time. The moment they get graduated and opens up to the world of 'Startups', they witness a huge gap between the reality and the theories they have learned. We educate children for a better job with technologies and lots more but the world they have to encounter with is really a contrary version of what they have thought of. The youngsters equipped with obsolete weapon/ strategies are thrown out by labeling them as 'good for nothing' 'not fit for the job' and so on. Hence, the need of developing our education system to fit to the 21st century indeed is a necessity and being emphasized by UNESCO in 1991 itself and it is the hottest topic which needs the right

attention. Youths have the potentiality to move the world to build up a healthy and peaceful environment in the societies. But to bring up the potentialities in youth, the nations should take an oath to provide quality education that shape students with relevant skills to meet the challenges of the world. This transformative vision of education will be fulfilled only through right education. A right education in 21st century which include the development of 21st century skills, the evaluation pattern and lots to count.

Education in the new Era

"Every word is endowed with a spirit, therefore the speaker or expounder should carefully deliver his words at the appropriate time and place, for the impression which each word makeths is clearly evident and perceptible." (Bahai Writings)

The advent of the internet has unleashed forces in our world that we are challenged to harness in a meaningful and constructive way. At one level there is no doubt that the internet is a tremendous instrument in bringing about greater unity and integration but "learning to utilize the Internet in a manner conducive to material and spiritual progress is an immense challenge." Technology and financial supports alone will not be enough for today's challenges but quality education in the proper direction should be made mandatory for it to build a civilization that is materially and spiritually prosperous.

Survey reports by UNESCO discussed the needs of today's youth as follows

- Youth needs to move from traditional to international- from 3Rs to beyond that.
- Need to be more responsible and critical.
- New approaches and modalities.

Hence, UNESCO's members have come up with a few changes for Quality education which entails:

- Curricular changes
- Changes in evaluative techniques
- Proper educational plans, policies and designs
- Education for sustainable development

The Pathway from 3Rs to 4Cs

The basic skills, 3Rs, in the ancient years, were emphasized a lot due to its ever advancing need in knowledge generation. But in the science and technological era of great 'Doers', just mastering the 3Rs won't fetch any success to the youngsters whereas the new era upholds the necessity of 3Rs being boldly supported by the 21st century skills- especially the 4Cs. Education hitherto given prominence to such basic skills had transferred its attention towards developing the 21st century skills to make the students cope with their future successfully. 'James Burns' was rephrasing the 3Rs into a different version which needs attention- 3Rs instead of 'Reading, wRiting and aRithmetic' into 'Respect, Responsibility and Relationship' which should trigger the young minds. The new age of technology is in an oblivion towards the values. Social Media outburst have made people to openly distress the feelings of others without any bit of guilt. Anyone in the world can harm anyone of you with a fraction of second. The descent of public discourse into greater enmity enlarged the gap in relations- with societies, nations and so on.

UNESCO had urged the nations to be prepared for the coming of 'the end of century' through their report 'Education for 21st Century' in 1991. This report, in an earlier time, foreseen the problems of the education system and proposed an education system that will fit in to the 21st century needs and necessities. Years later, in 2015, the focus of UNESCO shifted towards the soft skills and other mandatory skills to be developed in students by terming those as 21st century skills. The (Learning Skills) 4C Skills- Critical Thinking, Creativity, Communication and Collaboration- are majorly emphasized, along with the Literary Skills and Life Skills, in recent years.

English- the Lingua Franca of the Era

Effective communication is the heart of every endeavor. To reach the population, communication is the best tool. To tackle problems, to negotiate, to adopt and adapt, to befriend and so on. The Global nature of English language help youngsters to build up their confidence to meet the challenges they face. Knowledge of English- the Library language- improves and increases one's knowledge in different area as the reservoir of knowledge can be found easily in English language than the native languages of others. The world is interconnected with the help of technology. Now the boundaries of nations are not really a boundary for communication. When the outburst of internet-chatting, video calling etc- helped youngsters to get more opportunities outside their country and could flourish their businesses into a vast interconnected world. With the advent of media such as, Facebook, Instagram and YouTube, people themselves have become international. Through online dealings and more they could commune with people of different land. Hence, the importance of a Lingua Franca truly is a blessing. We are aware that the Lingua Franca of 21st Century is English indeed.

Communication skill in English, especially, is an invaluable skill. Mushrooming of spoken English classes, coaching etc are the clear evidence of it. In the world of ‘Startups’, multinational companies, corporate sectors etc rely mainly on English to attract clients and customers nationally and internationally and to prosper and progress in their business. Efficient English communication fetches high profile and high demand in this technological era.

Competent English speaking has a great impact on the future of students. Command over English language. To be successful in the 21st century, we need skills those are necessary for this century. The practiced ability only will turn in to skill. English language mastery provides confidence in order to practice and succeed in any skill in the 21st century. Success depends mainly on updating your knowledge base in the respective area which possible through mastery over English Language. Early exposure to English helps to polish a good command of the language. Living in a world of ICT - 21st century- it is essential to converse with people of different nationality which is possible only through a lingua franca- right now it’s other than English Language.

The Interconnection of 4Cs and the Lingua Franca (English)

- Critical thinking teaches students to pose queries and to investigate independently the truth.
- Creativity makes students to think divergently to produce something novel.
- Collaboration teaches students the importance of team work and its benefits.
- Communication teaches students to commune effectively to influence people.

It is evident that English language plays a vital role in developing these skills. The more one reads and comprehends the more will be his/her thinking process. When youngsters abreast with current information with the help of internet, it is to be appreciated. Right way of communication and mastery over English are some of the main determinants.

Mentor in the new Era

“Blessed is that teacher who shall arise to instruct the children, and to guide the people into the pathways of God, the Bestower, the Well-Beloved”

The requisite for building a better society starts from shaping the younger generation. One of the main determinants of that indeed is the teacher- the Mentor of new Era. A Mentor, in all aspects an exemplary personae to the students. The necessity of communication and the right way of talking should be penetrated into students mind through the mentor. The efficiency of a mentor in English language surely influences the students. This in turn make the students to master over the target

language. Along with being influential by the target language, knowledge of English helps the teacher to be a mentor in all its respect. Amassing information and keeping abreast with the new knowledge, innovations, and being a tech savvy help a mentor in all ways. Your knowledge of the content will be measured by your knowledge in English- the lingua franca, and the knowledge of recent innovations and technologies. 21st century students are far better than their teachers in technology and the 'Apps'. Hence, up-dating your knowledge is mandatory in which English is a desideratum in 21st century. MOOC courses helps these mentors in lifelong learning. Transacting mentor's expertise and experience, and socializing with each other is an important part of the educational system. Today's teachers are closely watched because of all of the changes in curriculum and the Common Core.

Evaluation of the new Era

One of the main threats of education system in improving the English language is its evaluation system. UNESCO recommended the nations to adopt a better evaluative system to suit 21st century. The advent of constructivism emphasized on learner centered curriculum, new approaches, methods, techniques and Models to attain the goal of student centric teaching-learning curricula but still when it comes to evaluation of languages- first language as well as the second and third, for that matter- no priority were given. The general objective of languages set aside for the specific objectives of the language comprehension. LSRW should be evaluated with its necessities by giving priority to each skill.

Desiderata to enhance English Language

- Well-equipped liberated class rooms where the intellectual curiosity and desire to learn English language is maintained.
- Don't be afraid of committing errors.
- Practice speaking skill then to other skills
- Practice polishes the skill
- Use JAM (Just A Minute) technique.
- Imaginary conversation in target language.
- Read articles and review it in target language
- Grammar Quiz application/online grammar quizzes.
- Self-evaluation.
- Be proud of learning the lingua franca
- Be optimistic and confident

Conclusion

Technology has shaped the ways we communicate; starting from print media to internet and in the future the artificial intelligence. In parallel with this, the Global nature of English- Globish has been uplifted and given importance in 21st century and to enhance the 21st century skills.

Reference:

- 1) **Cox, Janella (2019) Characteristics of a 21st-Century Teacher** retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/characteristics-of-a-21st-century-teacher-2081448>
- 2) **E2030: Education and Skills for the 21st Century (2017)** retrieved from <http://www.unesco.org/new/fileadmin/MULTIMEDIA/FIELD/Santiago/pdf/Habilidades-SXXI-Buenos-Aires-Eng.pdf>
- 3) **E2030: EDUCATION AND SKILLS FOR THE 21ST CENTURY (2017)** <http://www.unesco.org/new/fileadmin/MULTIMEDIA/FIELD/Santiago/pdf/Meeting-Report-Buenos-Aires-2017-E2030-LAC-ENG.pdf>
- 4) **‘Why Learning English Is So Important In The 21st Century’** retrieved from <https://www.englishexplorer.com.sg/why-learning-english-is-so-important-in-the-21st-century/>
- 5) **Thoughtful Learning: What are the 4 C's of learning skills?(2016)** retrieved from
- 6) <https://newsroom.unl.edu/announce/csmce/5344/29195>